

Analyzing the Design and Impact of Digital Serious Games in Digital Security: Challenges and Emerging Trends

This studies summarization is related to the SLR related to the aforementioned paper submitted for review to XV Simpósio Brasileiro de Jogos e Entretenimento Digital (SBGames 2026) - Goiania/GO

Paper Title	Reference	Paper's goal	Game platform	Game genre	Targeted audience	Participant Profile	Evaluation approach	Cybersecurity topics related to the game	Ethics Committee
CyberVR - An Interactive Learning Experience in Virtual Reality for Cybersecurity Related Issues	Veneruso et al. (2020)	Improve the user awareness of cybersecurity-related issues through CyberVR.	Oculus Rift (VR)	First-Person videogame / VR simulation	General Public	40 participants (adults aged 24-34)	Effectiveness and engagement	Information flow classification, code injection, patch management (software updates), dynamic software analysis, privilege escalation, public-key cryptography	Not explicitly mentioned
CyberKids: video game for raising cyber security awareness in children	Perez et al. (2020)	Design and develop CyberKids, a serious game to deliver educational content on cybersecurity to children.	Android (3D/2D)	Adventure	Primary and secondary education students	group of parent supervisors and children aged 8–12	evaluation form with a 1–10 rating scale, incipient validation with volunteers	Strong passwords, vulnerabilities identification, phishing, cyberbullying	Not explicitly mentioned
A NERD DOGMA: Introducing CTF to Non-expert Audience	Costa et al. (2020)	Introduce A NERD DOGMA as an entry-level CTF combined with an escape room game for beginners.	On-site facility and online web-based application	Capture the Flag (CTF) / Escape room	General Public / Primary and secondary education students (high school)	54 on-site participants + 72 high school students (online event)	anonymous feedback form with 3 questions on enjoyment, difficulty, and learning (1–5 scale)	Vulnerabilities, web technologies	Not explicitly mentioned
sD&D: Design and Implementation of Cybersecurity Educational Game with Highly Extensible Functionality	Kido et al. (2020)	Provide an inexpensive and easy tool for learning cybersecurity through a board game simulation called Security Defense and Dungeons (sD&D).	Network multiplayer (digital board game)	Board game simulation	Primary and secondary education students	Student users	Questionnaire (positive comments and opinions)	Authentication, access controls, network resources protection, cyberbullying prevention	Not explicitly mentioned
Cyber Shield Security Awareness Program	Abu-Amara et al. (2021)	Improve employees' security awareness by developing an interactive video game, Cyber Shield Game.	Web-based (Python/Django)	Interactive video game	Industry Professionals	10 employees randomly chosen from different institutions	Pre and post-game surveys	Password complexity, physical security, storage and disposal of confidential documents	Not explicitly mentioned
Criminal Investigations: An Interactive Experience to Improve Student Engagement and Achievement in Cybersecurity courses	Mohanty et al. (2021)	Teach and assess reverse-engineering and firmware analysis skills through a text-based interactive activity.	Web-based application (Cloud)	Text-based interactive activity	Undergraduate Students	Not explicitly stated	Not explicitly stated	Software reverse engineering, IoT firmware analysis	Not explicitly mentioned
Design, Development, and Evaluation of a Cybersecurity, Privacy, and Digital Literacy Game for Tweens	Maqsood and Chiasson (2021)	Teach children about cybersecurity, privacy, and digital literacy topics through A Day in the Life of the JOs.	Web-based (Desktop and iPads)	Simulated environment / Educational game	Primary and secondary education students	63 childs and 21 teachers	Summative evaluation (knowledge and behavioural intent)	Cyberbullying, data privacy, online reputation, privacy and ethics, verifying information	Approved by the Carleton University Research Ethics Board
It's a Fraud : Learning about Cybersecurity	Silva et al. (2022)	Raise awareness of internet security problems using the video game It's a Fraud.	Unity (2D)	2D Video game	General Public	~100 participantes (pre-game); 14 participants (pos-game)	Questionnaires (pre and post game surveys)	Spyware, computer virus, keylogger, Trojan horse, hacker	Not explicitly mentioned
Can gamification help to teach Cybersecurity?	Berisford et al. (2022)	Evaluate the efficacy of a bespoke gamified application in creating awareness and fostering an understanding of threats and secure coding practices in JavaScript.	Unity (desktop/laptop)	Gamified application	Undergraduate Students	9 students (First and second-year undergraduate students)	Awareness and technical proficiency, user engagement	Secure coding practices, JavaScript vulnerabilities, web application attacks	Not explicitly mentioned
NetDefense: A Tower Defense Cybersecurity Game for Middle and High School Students	Toledo et al. (2022)	Present NetDefense, a game designed to teach students basic cybersecurity concepts related to networking.	Unity3D / WebGL	Tower Defense	Primary and secondary education students	10 school teachers	Pre and post-game survey questions	Data packets, packet filtering, firewalls, honeypots, network log analysis	Not explicitly mentioned
Soceng Warriors: Game-Based Learning to Increase Security Awareness Against Social Engineering Attacks	Alma'ariz et al. (2022)	Raise security awareness of social engineering attacks using the educational game Soceng Warriors.	Android	Top-down RPG game with minigames	General Public	30 responders aged 14 to 25 years	Pre-test and post-test questionnaires (paired T-test)	Social engineering attacks	Not explicitly mentioned
A Cybersecurity Awareness Escape Room using Gamification Design Principles	DeCusatis et al. (2022)	Improve cybersecurity awareness through a virtual cybersecurity escape room.	Unity (3D)	Escape room	Pre-college and college students	90 pre-college students and 30 college students	Eight gamification metrics (Octalysis framework), playtesting results	Cybersecurity awareness, phishing attacks	Not explicitly mentioned
Housie: A Multiplayer Game for Cybersecurity Training and Evaluation	Jayakrishnan et al. (2022)	Bring organization's employees together and equip them with cybersecurity knowledge through Housie.	Web-based platform	Multiplayer Game (Bingo)	Industry Professionals	Over 56,000 participants (employees)	Cybersecurity awareness insights	General cybersecurity awareness	Not explicitly mentioned
CyberSafe: A Gamified Cyber Security Training Method	Salman et al. (2023)	Present CyberSafe to increase users' awareness and equip them with the necessary skills to mitigate the risk of cyberattacks.	Unity	Gamified training system	General Public	Not explicitly stated	Pre- and post-tests	password security, virus/malware detection, cyberattack types, safe internet navigation, cybersecurity awareness	Not explicitly mentioned

The Learning Outcomes Achievement and User Experience Analysis of a Cryptography Education Web Game	Susanto and Arifin (2024)	Develop an interactive web game that blends puzzle-solving with a visual novel to make cryptographic concepts more accessible.	Web-based platform	Puzzle-solving / Visual Novel	Undergraduate Students	30 participants	Pre-test and post-test scores, ARCS model (Attention, Relevance, Confidence, Satisfaction)	Cryptography, encryption, decryption, CIA triad (Confidentiality, Integrity, Availability)	Not explicitly mentioned
VPET: A Novel Visual Privacy Themed Cybersecurity Educational Game	Chattopadhyay et al. (2024)	Introduce a novel visual privacy themed game (VPET) to teach fundamental data privacy and basic security concepts.	Desktop-based application	Multiplayer / Disguise tasks	Primary and secondary education students and Teachers	School community members (high school students and teachers)	Survey responses evaluating learning, awareness, and interest	Visual privacy (VPET), applied cryptography for privacy-driven de-identification	Not explicitly mentioned
ForenSEEK: Gamifying Learning Experiences in Digital Forensics using Unity Engine and Augmented Reality Technology	Pantalano et al. (2024)	Encourage Filipino young adults to pursue careers in digital forensics or cybersecurity through ForenSEEK.	Unity Engine with Augmented Reality (AR)	AR Serious Game	Young Adults (18-30): undergraduate students and employees	150 young adults (113 students and 37 employees)	Pre-Test and Post-Test scores, Game User Experience Satisfaction Scale (GUESS)	Digital forensics (computer, cloud, network forensics)	Not explicitly mentioned
Encrypta: A missão da liga dos robôs - Um jogo educacional para aprendizagem em cibersegurança	de Abreu et al. (2024)	Protect teenagers from cyber attacks on the internet through the digital game Encrypta.	Web-based / Desktop (Electron)	Educational game	Primary and secondary education students	10 adolescents	MEEGA+ model (usability and player experience) and learning test (15-question multiple-choice quiz)	Strong passwords, phishing emails, malicious websites and files, regular backups	Not explicitly mentioned
AugmentWall: An AR Firewall Game for Concretizing Cybersecurity Concepts and Examining Student Engagement, Learning, and Motivation	Asif et al. (2025)	Enhance middle school cybersecurity education through interactive gameplay with AugmentWall.	Augmented Reality (AR)	AR Firewall Game	Primary and secondary education students	37 students across two schools	Engagement, comprehension, and perceived educational value (self-reported learning gains)	Firewall rules, network security	Approved by the University Institutional Review Board (IRB)
Enhancing Cybersecurity Learning with In-Game Feedback	Weeratunge and Hjelsvold (2025)	Teach Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) attacks through The XSS Game (TXG).	Web-based platform	Multi-opposing-role-playing	Undergraduate Students	Experts (Expert evaluations)	Learner engagement and self-reflection	Cross-Site Scripting (XSS) attacks	No approval required (data collection did not involve personal data, per Sikt - Norwegian Agency for Shared Services in
Cracking Aegis: An Adversarial LLM-based Game for Raising Awareness of Vulnerabilities in Privacy Protection	Fu et al. (2025)	Raise awareness of privacy protection vulnerabilities using an adversarial LLM-based game.	LLM-based dialogue game	Adversarial dialogue-based serious game	General Public	22 participants	In-game textual inputs and interviews	Privacy protection, phishing, impersonation, oversharing personal data with AI	Approved by the Ethics Committee of Beijing Normal University
Cyber Defender: desenvolvimento e avaliação de um jogo educativo para ensino de segurança cibernética	dos Santos et al. (2025)	Support the teaching of fundamental digital security concepts through the educational game Cyber Defender.	PC (Windows and Linux)	Educational game	Undergraduate Students	18 participants (mostly CS students, average age 22, 16 male, 2 female)	MEEGA+, IAQJED, Pro-Avalia JS, and PAJED (usability, gameplay, user experience, educational impact, etc.)	phishing (Phase 1), ransomware (Phase 2), DDoS attacks (Phase 3)	a Free and Informed Consent Form (TCLE) is mentioned, but no formal Ethics Committee (CEP) is explicitly cited
CyberClash: Cybersecurity awareness game	Raturi et al. (2025)	Introduce a gamified cybersecurity awareness platform, CyberClash, to teach people about cyberthreats.	Web-based platform	Interactive gameplay / simulation	General Public	50 participants (college undergraduates, IT users, and non-IT users)	User's capacity to identify and react to attacks	Phishing, password management, digital hygiene	Not explicitly mentioned
CyberGuardian: A Role-Playing Educational Game for Learning Cryptographic Primitives in Authentic Cybersecurity Scenarios	Huang et al. (2025b)	Introduce students to foundational concepts in cybersecurity through authentic scenarios using CyberGuardian.	Desktop-based (offline)	Role-playing educational game	Undergraduate Students	Not explicitly stated	Pre- and post-tests, Likert questionnaires, and think-aloud studies	Cryptographic primitives (symmetric/asymmetric encryption, digital signature), adversarial thinking	Not explicitly mentioned
Meeting Mayhem: A Web-Based Educational Game Focused on Adversarial Thinking	Huang et al. (2025a)	Gently and non-technically introduce students to the Dolev-Yao network intruder model through MeetingMayhem.	Web-based platform	Role-playing / Adversarial game	Undergraduate Students	Not explicitly stated	Five-point Likert scale survey and interviews	Adversarial thinking, network security, cryptography	Not explicitly mentioned
Game On: A Developmental Approach to UNSW Cyber Escape Room for Cybersecurity Governance and Policy Education	Hasan et al. (2026)	Design, implementation, and evaluation of a 3D virtual serious game (UNSW Cyber Escape Room) tailored for cybersecurity governance and policy education.	3D virtual environment	Escape room	Undergraduate Students	20 participants	Post-activity perception survey (engagement, usability, and perceived learning effectiveness)	Cybersecurity governance and policy, analyzing cyber risks, aligning security frameworks, drafting policies	Approved by the UNSW Human Research Ethics Committee